

A Geographical Study Of Education Facilities In The Akole Tehsil District Ahmednagar, Maharashtra

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Abstract:

In the tahsil there are 341 number of education Institutes are available. Among of these primary educations maximum is 133 and Average distance in two schools is about 3.35K.m. Second position is Upper primary schools are 90 with the average distance in two schools is 4.08K.m. The Average distance tow education institutes are Polytechnic, MCA and B. Ed colleges about 19.36 K.M. and but of all education institutes average distance are 2.09 K.M.

Key words: Economic development, Education, Amenities, Human resources.

Introduction:

Economic development of a region is depending on the development of human and natural resources because of Man he develops with his knowledge, skilled and good health. The most important criteria of human resources development are population density, literacy, occupation, sex ratio etc. The base of geography is depending on the case study of human population and environmental elements. For the development of specific region or area, we used these knowledge resources. Resources mainly used for the origin of national, local economic and self-development. Human resources are one of the most important national resources and base for the study of population geography. Man has layout the resources on the earth's surface and main natural utility classified in rank. On the Earth, it are biotic and abiotic elements included in classified resources. Man always using the available resources for human development with the help of own skill. Man uses resources for himself development. Therefore, in the developing nation's population is increasing very rapidly.

(Mahesh 2012) The human resources are important vision for in terms of per capita income, life expectancy, education, per capita consumption of electricity and health facilities. (Spatarshi 1996, Gosal 1996, Spatarshi 1996, Mali 1996) Human Resources development has calculated with the help of several parameters like density of population, population growth rates, and literacy as alternate indicators of the quality of human resources. Health amenities are important for human resources development. (Gosal 1995) Population growth, literacy, education, technical education and health care facilities are important indicators for quantifying the human resources. The

human resources play the dynamic role in the development of natural resources. He has supported the idea in quality of man is the key factors in the whole of regional development. (Saptarshi 1996). Human resources development based on technological, social, cultural and economic elements. (Siddiqui 2010 and Hussain . 2014). The process of development involves a significant change in the economic activities over different region along with a change in the structure of economy. The identification of regional disparities and extend of inter Blocks disparities in different types like Education, Medical, Communication and Transportations, Market, Electricity and Drinking water, Agricultural, Finance, Recreational to use the Deprivation Index and Development Index or Deprivation Method Formula.

Study Area:

Geographically Ahmednagar district is the largest district in the state of Maharashtra, divided into 14 Tahsil. One of the Akole Tahsil which is on the western Hilly region of Ahmednagar district, it is divided into 191 villages. Four Revenue Circles namely Rajur, Akole, Samsherpur revenue circles and surrounded by Sangamner tahasil from East side, to the West side Thane district, to the North side Nashik district and in to the South direction Pune district. Well surrounded with the mountains range of Sahyadri in Western side. Akole Tahsil is located in 19°15' 14" N to 19° 44' 59" N latitude and 73° 37' 00" to 74° 07' 24" E longitudes (Map. No 2.1). Total Geographical area is 1, 49,990.31 hector (1499sq.K.M). Total population of this Tahsil is, 2, 7, 7 1, 71 in 2011 Census year, out of 1, 01,966 (ST) Tribal population is in this study area.

Map no: 01 Location map of study area

Amis And Objective:

The main objective for this research paper is how the level of education in Akole tehsil. Another main objective is to find out the average distance between these educational facilities.

Methodology:

Secondary data has been used to fulfill the main objective of this research paper. The above statistical information is taken from the Panchayat Samiti in Akola Tehsil, the statistical information has been processed and bar graph has been prepared and average distance method has been used.

Result:

Education:

Education is the vital characteristic of a nation for human resources development. Education is most significant used for a nation with area/region development. Moreover, peoples are development with modify social and economic status are changed. Education influence in averagely for all surrounding development and achievement of human life of man. Any levels of employment in a region the greater are both the quantity and the quality of education available.

The quality of population can be referring from life expectancy the level of literacy and the level of technical education make by the people of any country/ Region. (Gupta 1992) has describe that education formal as well as informal one of the introduction agent's community change particular between the

females by exposing them to outside world wading their possibility if with information about a lot of matters applicable to life. Education facilities are very essential for human resources developments and their close relationships in level of human resources development. Education level depends on the accessibility in education facilities. The education amenities are open challenge in human resources development because of all good reference in these amenities in a human life. The availability of various education facilities in the as well as the all the villages are and have education availability.

Average Distance:

The average distance between two schools calculated to find out relationship between educational facilities and human resources development. The inter institution distance may be one of the indicator of accessibility of education facilities in a region. (Pawar D.H 2009) Average Distance sued for the spacing of rural settlement. Thus, recharger uses in this formula each educational institution with averagely distance in the study area. In the tahsil there are 341 number of education Institutes are available. Among of these primary educations maximum is 133 and Average distance in two schools is about 3.35K.m. Second position is Upper primary schools are 90 with the average distance in two schools is 4.08K.m. The Average distance tow education institutes are Polytechnic, MCA and B. Ed colleges about 19.36 K.M.

and but of all education institutes average distance are 2.09 K.M.

Graph no: 01 Education amenities in Akole tehsil

Conclusion:

The identification of regional disparities and extend of inter Blocks disparities in different types like Education, Medical, Communication and Transportations, Market, Electricity and Drinking water, Agricultural, Finance, Recreational to use the Deprivation Index and Development Index In the tahsil there are 341 number of education Institutes are available. Among of these primary educations maximum is 133 and Average distance in two schools is about 3.35K.m. Second position is Upper primary schools are 90 with the average distance in two schools is 4.08K.m. The Average distance tow education institutes are Polytechnic, MCA and B. Ed colleges about 19.36 K.M. and but of all education institutes average distance are 2.09 K.M.

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